

RES TERRAE

Publications in Geosciences, University of Oulu
Oulun yliopiston geotieteiden julkaisuja

Ser. A, No. 49
2024

MINEARC WEBINAR Mineral resource and sustainable exploration 23–24 April 2024 Abstracts

Shenghong Yang, Nils Jansson, and Juha Kaija eds.

MINEARC WEBINAR

A clustering event of mineral exploration projects and industry.

FREE REGISTRATION

MINEARC

23-24 APRIL | ONLINE

MINERAL RESOURCES & SUSTAINABLE EXPLORATION

One-and-a-half days online event bringing academia, research projects and industry together, to discuss the development of sustainable exploration methods, technological and societal challenges and solutions in exploration sector.

THE EVENT IS CO-ORGANIZED BY:
MINEARC, SEMACRET, EIS, AGEMERA & MINEXTARGET

MINEARC WEBINAR Mineral resource and sustainable exploration,
23–24 April 2024, Abstracts

Shenghong Yang, Nils Jansson, and Juha Kaija eds.

Res Terrae, Ser. A, No. 49, OULU, 2024

RES TERRAE - Publications in Geosciences, University of Oulu,
Oulun yliopiston geotieteiden julkaisuja

Ser. A, Contributions, Ser. B, Raportteja - Reports, Ser. C, Opetusjulkaisuja -
Teaching material

Ser. A	ISSN 0358-2477 (print)
Ser. A	ISSN 2489-7957 (online)
Ser. B	ISSN 0358-2485 (print)
Ser. B	ISSN 2736-9552 (online)
Ser. C	ISSN 0358-2493 (print)
Ser. A, No. 49	ISBN 978-952-62-4106-7 (online)

Editorial board - Toimituskunta:
Dr. Kirsi Luolavirta, Päätoimittaja - Editor-in-Chief
Dr. Ninna Immonen

Julkaisu ja levitys - Published and distributed by:
Oulu Mining School
P.O. Box 3000, 90014 University of Oulu, Finland

E-mail: kirsi.luolavirta@oulu.fi
www: <http://www.oulu.fi/resterr/>

Mineral systems driven prospectivity modelling of orthomagmatic ore deposits

Aranha, M.¹, Yang, S.¹, Kozlovskaya, E.¹, Guo, F.¹, Virtanen, V.³, Booth, C.⁴, Silvennoinen H.², Jackson, M.⁴, Maier, W.⁵, Iacono, G.³ and Sarala, P.¹,

¹Oulu Mining School, University of Oulu, Finland, malcolm.aranha@oulu.fi

²Sodankylä Geophysical Observatory, University of Oulu, Finland.

³Institute des Sciences de la Terre d'Orléans (ISTO), CNRS-Université d'Orléans-BRGM, France

⁴Imperial College of London, United Kingdom.

⁵Cardiff University, United Kingdom.

Nickel (Ni), cobalt (Co), platinum group metals (PGMs), chromium (Cr), vanadium (V), and copper (Cu) are some of the metals that are considered critical or strategic raw materials by the European Commission and are hosted in orthomagmatic ore deposits. The SEMACRET project aims to develop responsible exploration methods for such critical metals within the EU and beyond to ensure a consistent supply for the green energy transition.

This contribution describes geological modelling of such deposits following the concept of mineral systems which includes (1) fertile magma sources, (2) pathways for magma transport, and (3) mechanisms of metal deposition, followed by its application to regional-scale exploration targeting. The study area is in the Lapland area in northern Finland, hosting two types of orthomagmatic mineralisation – layered mafic intrusions-hosted PGM-Cr-V-(Co-Ni-Cu) and conduit-type Ni-Cu-(PGM-Co) sulphide deposits (Maier and Hanski, 2017).

There is ongoing debate regarding the sources of mafic-ultramafic magma, with isotopic systems like Re-Os and Sm-Nd serving as valuable tools in distinguishing different mantle sources. Preliminary results suggest that plume or asthenospheric mantle is the primary source of such magmas. This inference is supported by geochemical and thermodynamic modelling, particularly focusing on plume magmatism in Fennoscandia (e.g., Guo et al., 2023). The process of magma transport is being modelled numerically, with a focus on underplating and the formation of magma reservoirs. Magma fractionation and assimilation processes are studied using petrological analysis and thermodynamic simulations with implications for exploration. High-temperature experimental studies are conducted to explore the interaction between sulphur-bearing rocks and magma.

Regional exploration targeting involves compiling mineral system models incorporating all crucial ore-forming processes for the two types of orthomagmatic mineral deposits. Targeting models are then generated based on these mineral system models, identifying specific targeting criteria for the Lapland study area considering the scale of the study area and the datasets available. Spatial data processing and GIS analysis tools are used to map spatial proxies of each targeting criterion, generating predictor maps. Openly available geoscientific datasets are utilised for analysis, demonstrating the widespread applicability of the workflow. In addition to commonly used geodata (e.g., gravity, magnetic, and surficial geochemistry), the project aims at generating novel proxies and data sources for prospectivity modelling. This includes interpreting seismic data to understand the lithospheric structure, mapping craton boundaries to represent transient geodynamic settings, and using structural data to represent fault density as focal points of magmatic flow accumulation. These predictor maps are then integrated using Fuzzy Inference Systems (FIS; Porwal et al., 2015), an artificial intelligence-based algorithm, to generate prospectivity maps.

Preliminary results show good agreement of the model with known metal occurrences, with high-prospective areas identified in the north-central and western parts of the study area. These areas are recommended for further detailed exploration to narrow down target areas for eventual ground exploration.

References:

- Guo, F.F., Maier, W.D., Heinonen, J.S., Hanski, E., Vuollo, J., Barnes, S.J., Lahaye, Y., Huhma, H. and Yang, S., 2023. Geochemistry of 2.45 Ga mafic dykes in northern Finland: Constraints on the petrogenesis and PGE prospectivity of coeval layered intrusions. *Lithos*, 452, p.107206.
- Maier, W.D. and Hanski, E.J., 2017. Layered Mafic–Ultramafic Intrusions of Fennoscandia: Europe's Treasure Chest of Magmatic Metal Deposits. *Elements: An International Magazine of Mineralogy, Geochemistry, and Petrology*, 13(6), pp.415-420.
- Porwal, A., Das, R.D., Chaudhary, B., Gonzalez-Alvarez, I., Kreuzer, O., 2015. Fuzzy inference systems for prospectivity modeling of mineral systems and a case-study for prospectivity mapping of surficial Uranium in Yeelirrie Area, Western Australia. *Ore Geology Reviews*, 71, pp.839-852.